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Feasibility of implementing Active Acoustic Emission (AAE) Technology to Monitoring the Crack Healing Process of Asphalt Concrete (AC)

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ABSTRACT

Active Acoustic Emission (AAE) is a non-destructive test (NDT) technique used for monitoring crack initiation detection and the progress of internal damage at the microscopic scale. In this assessment, specimens of asphalt concrete (AC) were prepared with optimum binder requirements using Marshall method. Specimens were tested for fatigue using PRLS (pneumatic repeated load system) at 20°C environment and monitored through AAE technology. Dynamic indirect tensile stress (DITS) was applied to the diametral specimen, and the vertical strain is recorded after each load repetition. A constant loading frequency of 60 cycles per minute was applied. Each load cycle is 0.9 sec rest period and 0.1 sec load duration. The ultrasound pulse velocity (USPV) after 600 and 1200 load repetitions was recorded. Testing was terminated after 1200 load repetitions, and the specimens were withdrawn from the PRLS chamber and stored in an oven at 60 °C for 120 minutes to allow microcrack healing. Specimens were returned to the testing chamber and subjected to second round of load repetitions. It was observed that the USPV declined after practicing 1200 repetitions of indirect tensile stresses by (26, 14.2, and 12.3) % for wearing, binder, and base courses mixtures respectively as compared with their control mixtures. However, after practicing crack healing, USPV increased by (13.5, 25.8, and 2.3) % for wearing, binder, and base courses mixtures respectively. Deterioration of the mixtures was monitored through AAE technology and modeled. AAE technology is recommended for prediction the damage behavior of AC through its fatigue life.

Keywords: Active acoustic emissions (AAE), asphalt concrete (AC), modelling, dynamic stress, indirect tensile strength. USPV

INTRODUCTION

Stringent quality control is usually implemented during AC pavement construction. Before approving the quality of the pavement, core specimens are usually obtained to verify the thickness, density, and various volumetric properties and strength of the executed AC mixture. Such sampling techniques and testing are time and labor consuming. Implication of innovative NDT is considered as a desirable method for evaluating the in-situ condition of pavement structures since it does not cause any disruption to traffic system or causes damage to the surface or structure of the pavement. NDT may be implemented for quick collection of test data. It is treated as a consistent and reliable testing technique as addressed by Sarsam and Kadium, [1]. Several NDT techniques are available and could be applied in the field or laboratory for AC mixtures. The fundamental principle of acoustic emission (AE) test is based on the detection and analysis of transient elastic waves produced by the rapid release of energy from localized sources within the structure of a material. Such elastic waves could be present on their own (passive acoustic emission testing PAE, which requires no intervention) or could be introduced by stressing a material (active acoustic emission testing AAE, which requires an intervention from the inspector to create acoustic waves) as reported by Hashim et al., [2]; Wei et al., [3]; and Seo and Kim, [4]. Two types of acoustic emission techniques(AE)exists, the first one is the active acoustic emission (AAE) technique in which an ultrasound wave is transmitted and propagate through the AC specimen and recieved by transducers through a fixed distance and the time

required for the ultrasound wave to propagate through the specimen is recorded and the velocity of propagation is calculated. The second technique is the passive acoustic emission PAE in which an energy is rapidly released from a localized damage source within a material, resulting in transient elastic waves. The elastic waves signals that are excited by irreversible processes, such as crack nucleation and propagation. These signals are sensed by transducers and are transformed into electric waveforms that offer information on the location and the type of the source as addressed by Xiang et al., [5], Qiu et al., [6]. Stress waves are scattered and can be detected at the material's surface. The AE system is a widely used method addressed by Qiu et al., [7]. Application of AE system for characterizing AC mixtures started late, however, the behavior of AC in fracture can be monitored through the variation in AE parameters. Such concept has gradually been applied to the work on the mechanical and physical performance of AC and is widely accepted. Pulses of AE are generated at one side of the tested AC specimen by a transmitter device and then received at opposite side of the AC specimen by a receiver sensor. Through the analysis of the AE signals characteristics, the physical and mechanical behaviors of AC materials can be assessed for evaluating the changes inside the AC materials at the microscopic level, while it cannot be reflected from the physical macroscopic parameters including the strain-stress curve. Using NDT techniques for evaluating AC quality has been studied by Tavassoti-Kheiry et al., [8]. It was stated that application of (AE), and ultrasonic pulse wave velocity (USPV)

tests are some examples towards characterization of AC mixtures. The DMAC mix was assessed by Majhi et al., [9] using USPV by preparing the AC samples in laboratory, considering sample's geometric and bulk densities respectively. Testing results revealed that high significance of the test data was obtained by considering the bulk density. An AE approach to study the cracking behavior at low-temperature cracking of AC mixtures was investigated by Behnia et al., [10]. It was concluded that two AE characteristic temperatures were sensitive to the type of AC mixture and the oxidative ageing levels of the AC mixture. The AE is considered as one of the NDT techniques which can detect damage and deformations inside AC mixture by using the preamplifier and high-speed digital AE detector as reported by Xie et al., [11]. The signals which were received by the sensors were shown and converted by corresponding parameters. Recently, AE technique was widely implemented in the study of brittle and homogeneous materials including concrete and AC. Semi-circle bending test was conducted by Yang et al., [12] on AC specimens at cold environmental temperature and the AE parameters and characteristics were collected and analyzed throughout the test. Damage to the AC mixture was assessed. The dynamic evolution of fracture development in the mixture was assessed by various periods with the aid of source location of AE. It was concluded that AE signals mainly originate due to crack damage, which was caused by ITS, while the number of signals and their strength represent the degree of development of the cracking. Splitting tensile and compression tests on AC mixtures were carried out by

Jiao et al., [13] and obtained the AE parameter. The test results exhibited AC characteristics for each parameter had exhibited a relationship with the macro-damage of the AC mixture while AE technology showed great potential in characterizing the damage of AC mixture. The monitoring of self-healing ability of AC mixture by AE was investigated by Behnia and Reis, [14]; the test results exhibited that cooling of the AC mixture can reduce its self-healing ability. AE was recommended to be used for analysis of the effect of the rest period between the applied cycles of cooling on the energy for fracture of AC materials. Specimens of AC of various pavement courses were prepared by Sarsam and Kadhim, [15] and tested for ITS and Marshall properties. Specimens were subjected to USPV testing using the pundit instrument before practicing the physical strength test. The dynamic and seismic moduli were evaluated based on the USPV. A linear statistical model which can explain 75.4 % of the strength variation and can relate such properties with USPV of AC was obtained. The behavior of accumulation of damage of AC mixture was assessed by Qiu et al. [16] and verified the position of damage with the aid of AE location technology. Test results indicated that AE may be implemented to explain the behavior of AC mixtures during fracture. Two ultrasonic wave tests were used by Hou et al., [17] to assess AC physical, mechanical, and acoustic behavior. Relationships between such properties were analyzed and established. A wave velocity mathematical model in viscoelastic and isotropic material was established. It was concluded that USPV testing can be implemented for rapid and

NDT evaluation of material properties. As stated by Qiu et al., [18], the (AE) is a kind of (NDT) method, which can effectively detect minor damages of various AC mixtures. AE is a transient elastic wave generated in the AC mixture by the rapid release of stress energy when distress occurs in the AC mixture. Various waveforms and parameters characteristics were obtained from AE signals which can characterize material property and describe its damage behavior. Failure mode and other properties of AC mixture were investigated by Wei et al., [19]. The failure process was monitored through (AE). Typical characteristic parameters include hit, energy and amplitude were analyzed. Results addressed that the compressive strength and failure load of the AC mixtures increase as the rate of loading increases. The adopted frequency of AE signals was concentrated within 50-350 kHz, from the start of loading the AC mixtures to the whole failure process. It was concluded that mode of failure of the AC under different rates of loading may be verified based on the correlation difference of AE parameters. Four points bending fatigue test were performed by Wei et al., [20] on the AC mixture using the (AE) technique to analyze the damage evolution. It was stated that the analytical methods can enable an effective identification of fatigue damage in AC mixtures at the laboratory scale. The fatigue behaviors of AC were characterized by Wei et al., [21] through data analysis and integrated experimentation using four-point bending tests combined with monitoring by AE. A series of parameters were extracted from the AE signals to characterize the damage stages. Results showed that cracking due to tensile stresses comprised over 89% of

events. Performance of AC mixture in fracture was assessed by Song et al., [22] with (AE) monitoring and microstructural characterization. Results revealed that (AE) analysis highlighted the failure mechanisms. It was stated that the microstructural improvements correlated with macro-scale performance gains. (AE) and USPV techniques were integrated by Chen et al., [23] to evaluate thermal damage in concrete and proposed the shear-to-pressure wave velocity ratio to correlate with toughness, stiffness, and strength. It was concluded that combining USPV and (AE) techniques to link macroscopic mechanical properties with microscopic fracture mechanisms is sound. The behavior of AC mixtures in fracture at intermediate temperatures was investigated by Song et al., [24] with (AE) monitoring. Analysis of AE-derived cumulative energy/count and fracture energy revealed that tensile cracks are dominant. Test results exhibited the impact of mixture composition on AE response, providing insights for optimizing AC mixture design to enhance cracking resistance at intermediate temperature.

The aim of this work is to study the feasibility of use and monitor the impact of microcracks healing of AC pavement layers on DMAC and the damage through fatigue life with the aid of AAE technology. The deterioration of the AC mixtures through fatigue life will be monitored through AAE technology and modeled. The distinction from true passive AAE is that the energy, frequency, hit-based AAE will not be measured. Travel-time-based active ultrasonics and transmission-receive technique will be implemented.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Asphalt Cement

Asphalt cement binder with a penetration of 43 (PG 64-16) was collected from Al-Dura oil refinery. Physical properties of

the binder are shown in Figure 1. The testing was conducted as per the prescribed procedures by ASTM, [25].

Fig. 1: Properties of Asphalt Cement.

Fine and Coarse Aggregates

The aggregates (fine and Coarse) were obtained from Al-Nibae quarry; Figure 2 illustrates their properties. The testing was conducted according to ASTM, [25] procedures.

Fig. 2: Properties of Aggregates.

Mineral Filler

The limestone dust was used as a mineral filler; it was collected from Karbala. The bulk specific gravity is 2.617, while the percent finer than 75 micron is 94 %.

Combined Gradation of AC

The selected aggregates gradation in the present work follows the SCRB, [26] requirements for dense graded (wearing,

binder, and base) course with (12.5, 19, and 25.4) mm nominal maximum size of aggregates respectively. Figure 3 shows various investigated aggregate gradations.

Preparation of AC mixture

The AC mixture for each pavement layer was prepared according to Marshall test procedure presented in ASTM, [25]. Specimens of 63.5 mm in thickness and

102 mm in diameter were prepared. Figure 4 exhibits some part of the prepared AC specimens. Table 1 exhibits the properties of the prepared AC mixtures. Specimens of base course were prepared by practicing

50 blows of Marshall hammer on each side while binder and wearing courses specimens were subjected to 75 blows of Marshall hammer on each side.

Fig. 3: Aggregates gradation of asphalt concrete mixtures according to SCRB, [23]

Fig. 4: The prepared AC specimens.

Tables 1: Marshall Properties of the prepared AC Mixtures.

Marshall property	Wearing course	Binder course	Base course
Optimum binder content (%)	5	4.7	4
Marshall stability (kN)	11	11	9.5
Marshall flow (mm)	3.26	3.7	2.5
Bulk density (gm/Cm ³)	2.360	2.37	2.34
Air voids (%)	4	4	4
VMA (%)	14	14.5	14.5
Vfb (%)	78	72.5	73
Number of tested specimens	30	30	30

DITS Test

DITS test as prescribed by ASTM, [25] was conducted using (PRLS). Figure 5 presents the PRLS testing chamber. It is conventional fracture tests which can obtain certain macroscopic parameters such as deformation and strength properties but fail to clearly represent the internal damage development inside the specimen within its dimensions during the fracture process, crack initiation, and microcrack propagation until failure. The test was conducted on cylindrical specimens (63.5 mm in thickness and 102 mm in diameter). Dynamic indirect tensile stress was applied to the diametral specimen, and the vertical strain is recorded after each load repetition. A constant loading frequency of 60 cycles per minute and the loading sequence for each cycle is 0.9 sec rest period and 0.1 sec load duration. The testing chamber provided medium temperatures of 20 °C throughout the test. The behavior of AC mixtures throughout the fatigue process

under DITS is affected by intermediate service temperatures (15–25°C), during which the viscoelastic properties of the asphalt cement binder undergo significant changes as addressed by Weldegiorgis and Tarefder, [27]. The DITS repetitions were applied under constant stress level of 0.138 MPa. Specimens' conditions were monitored through AE technology before the application of DITS, and after 600 and 1200 load repetitions. The stress repetitions were limited to 1200 based on previous work reported by Sarsam and Husain, [28]; Sarsam and Kadium, [29]. Cracking in asphalt mixtures usually starts in the form of microcrack within 1000-1200 repetitions of stresses, while the cracking pattern changes to macrocrack after 1200 repetitions as documented by Sarsam, [30] and Roque et al, [31]. Dynamic modulus (DM) (it is also called complex modulus) is a property of viscoelastic materials. It is the ratio of stress to strain under vibratory conditions as stated by Malik, [32].

Fig. 5: PRLS test chamber.

Microcrack Healing Process

The adopted microcrack healing process was conducted through external heating system. After practicing the DITS for 1200 repetitions to allow for the initiation of microcracks, the testing was terminated. AC specimens were removed from the PRLS testing chamber and stored in an electric controlled oven at 60 °C environment for 120 minutes to allow for microcrack healing as reported by Sarsam and Husain, [33]; Ajam, [34]. Healing of microcracks of AC mixture usually occurs due to the reduction in the viscosity of asphalt binder by external heating allowing the flow of the binder through the microcracks. After the possible microcracks healing process, the AC specimens were allowed to cool in the room environment for 24 hours, then returned to the PRLS testing chamber. Specimens of AC were conditioned for two hours at 20° C environment inside the PRLS chamber. AC specimens were then subjected to second round of 1200 DITS repetitions cycle. The specimens were monitored by AE technology while practicing the DITS before and after the crack healing process using USPV determination. AC specimens prepared

with optimum binder requirements for each type of pavement layer were tested in triplicate, and the average value was considered for analysis. The accepted standard deviation was 5 % for the accepted testing results for such a limited testing program.

AAE Technique

The Pundit (portable ultrasonic non-destructive digital indicating tester) which generates and receives USPV waves through direct transmission arrangement was used in the present investigation as an AAE technique according to, ASTM, [35] as presented in Figure 6. The pundit is used through direct transmission arrangement with a frequency of 54 kHz and accuracy of 0.1 for measurement of the USPV through the AC specimens. The time consumed by the pulse to traverse the specimen was measured accurately and recorded. The USPV was calculated by dividing the thickness of the specimen (distance between the transducers) by the measured time. Eight readings were performed for each AC specimen and averaged for each of the triplicate specimen.

Fig. 6: The Pundit and the AAE technology

DISCUSSION OF TEST RESULTS

Variation of DM with Mixture Type under AAE Technology

Figure 7 shows the variations in the DM of AC with mixture type as evaluated by AAE technology. It can be observed that a variable AAE monitoring range of the USPV of (2.5-4), (3.25-4.45), and (3.5-4.25) mm/microseconds are presented for

(wearing, binder, and base) AC courses respectively. However, AAE monitoring range of the DM of (14-37), (25-45), and (27-40) GPa are presented for (wearing, binder, and base) courses respectively. Such variations in the monitoring ranges are related to the coarseness or fineness of the gradation of AC mixtures.

Fig. 7: Variation of DM and USPV with pavement layer type

Table 2 demonstrates the modeling of the variation of DM and USPV with AC pavement layer type. The polynomial mathematical models exhibit high

coefficients of determination which indicate their suitability for prediction of the DM for various mixtures with different gradation patterns.

Table 2: Modeling the variation of DM and USPV with AC pavement layer type.

AC Pavement layer type	Mathematical model	Coefficient of determination R2
Wearing course	$Y = 2.7997 X^2 - 2.9151 X + 3.2339$	0.977
Binder course	$Y = 1.4696 X^2 + 6.1848 X - 11.401$	0.9725
Basr course	$Y = 2.592 X^2 - 1.8578 X + 2.9188$	0.997

Y = DM, (GPa); X = USPV (mm/microsecond)

Influence of Microcrack Healing on Fatigue and Damage Resistance of AC

The damage and healing indicators of different courses of AC mixtures measured with the aid of AAE technology could be observed through the specimens constructed with optimum binder content.

Figure 8 demonstrates the effect of microcrack self-healing of AC throughout its fatigue process. It can be noticed that the USPV declined as the fatigue process under DITS proceeds regardless of the type of AC mixture. This could be attributed to the fact that the damage

initiated in the AC specimens and the vertical plastic strain under each repetition of load rises. The USPV declined after practicing 1200 repetitions of DITS by (26, 14.2, and 12.3) % for wearing, binder, and base courses mixtures respectively when it is compared with the control mixture before loading. However, when the AC specimens practiced the crack healing process, higher USPV could be observed which indicates healing of the microcracks due to microcrack being closer and enhancement of the quality of the mixtures after the healing process. Such findings may be related to the reduction of voids in the mixture by crack healing, which exhibited an increase in the cohesion between the particles of aggregate. The USPV after practicing 1200 repetitions of DITS and after practicing the crack healing increased by (13.5, 25.8, and 2.3) % for wearing, binder, and base courses mixtures respectively as compared with the AC specimens before healing. It can be observed that the impact of microcracks healing is more pronounced as the nominal maximum size of aggregates rises and the gradation is coarser, the mixture of base course pavement layer with 25.4 mm nominal

maximum size of aggregates exhibit the highest improvement in the USPV value before practicing the DITS of 19.2 % while the improvement in the USPV values for the mixture of binder course layer with nominal maximum size of aggregates of 19 mm and the mixture of wearing course layer with maximum size of aggregates of 12.5 mm are (12.8, and 3.6) % respectively. This may be related to the lower V_{fb} in the lower layers which can practice healing by filling more voids with binder during the healing process even before loading. Coarser mixes (Base course) may develop wider, more discrete microcracks upon damage, whereas finer mixes (Wearing course) may develop a more diffuse network of smaller microcracks. The flow of binder at 60°C (healing) may be more effective at "stitching" the wider cracks, leading to a larger relative recovery in USPV, while the smaller, more numerous cracks in the fine mixture are less effectively healed. AAE test data varied for different AC specimens; however, the laws of AAE parameters and variation characteristics were consistent. Such findings agree well with the reported work by Sarsam, [30]; Roque, [31] and Sarsam and Husain, [33].

Fig. 8: Self-healing through the fatigue process of AC.

Influence of Microcrack Healing on Rate of Decline in USPV

Figure 9 demonstrates the rate of variation of USPV through fatigue life of AC mixtures. A gentle decline in the USPV could be observed while practicing the DITS up to 100 repetitions, however, the rate of decline changed sharply until reaching the failure stage regardless of the type of AC mixture. The variation in the rate of decline in the USPV before and after the healing process among various types of AC mixtures is significant. The improvement due to healing in the USPV

at the start of loading is (2.7, 14.7, and 41.6) % for (wearing, binder, and base) courses mixtures respectively. However, the improvement due to healing in the USPV at the failure stage is (14.2, 27.5, and 4.7) % for (wearing, binder, and base) courses mixtures respectively. Such behavior could be related to variation in the nominal maximum size of aggregates which changes from small to large, and to the type of gradation which changes from fine to medium and coarse for (wearing, binder, and base) courses respectively.

Fig. 9: Variation of USPV through fatigue life

Table 3 exhibits the mathematical linear deterioration models of USPV of various types of AC mixtures through their fatigue process as obtained with the aid of AAE technology before and after practicing the

Microcrack healing process. The linear mathematical models were obtained with reasonable coefficients of determination. Similar findings were reported by Wei et al., [20].

Table 3: Deterioration models.

Mixture type	Before Healing	R ²	After Healing	R ²
Wearing course	Y= - 0.0008 X + 3.952	0.78	Y= - 0.0006 X + 4.052	0.79
Binder course	Y= - 0.0004 X + 3.502	0.79	Y= - 0.0001 X + 3.875	0.98
Base course	Y= - 0.0003 X + 2.427	0.97	Y= - 0.0009 X + 3.434	0.83

Y= USPV (mm/microsecond); X= Nf (load repetitions to failure)

Healing Index

The healing index in AC mixtures is a quantitative measure used to evaluate the material ability to self-repair the initiated microcracks and recover its mechanical properties after sustaining damage. It is

typically expressed as a ratio or percentage of the material property after a healing period to its original property before damage. It was determined for the various AC mixtures based on the mathematical equation (1) and presented in Table 4.

$$\text{Healing index (\%)} = [\text{USPV after healing} / \text{original USPV before damage}] \times 100\% \text{ -----(1)}$$

Table 4: Healing index.

Type of AC pavement layer	Wearing course	Binder course	Base course
Healing index (%) after loading	114.2	125.4	102.3
Healing index (%) before loading	103.9	113.2	137.5

It can be observed that the healing index after loading increases as the gradation of the AC mixture gets coarser. The healing index is (103.9, 113.2, and 137.5) % for (wearing, binder, and base) AC courses respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the applied testing program and materials limitations, the following remarks could be addressed.

- 1-The USPV declined after practicing 1200 repetitions of DITS by (26, 14.2, and 12.3) % for (wearing, binder, and base) AC mixtures courses respectively as compared with control mixtures.
- 2-The USPV after practicing 1200 repetitions of DITS and after practicing the crack healing process increased by (13.5, 25.8, and 2.3) % for (wearing, binder, and base) courses mixtures respectively as compared with those before healing.
- 3- Influence of microcracks healing is more pronounced as the nominal maximum size of aggregates rises and the gradation is coarser, the USPV after healing and before practicing the

DITS is improved by (3.6, 12.8, and 34.8) % for (wearing, binder, and base) courses respectively.

- 4- The improvement in the USPV due to healing at the start of loading is (2.7, 14.7, and 41.6) % for (wearing, binder, and base) courses mixtures respectively. However, such improvements after healing at the failure stage are (14.2, 27.5, and 4.7) % for (wearing, binder, and base) courses mixtures respectively.
- 5- The healing index before and after practicing the DITS was (103.9, 113.2, and 137.5) % and (114.2, 125.4, and 102.3) % for (wearing, binder, and base) courses respectively.
- 6- The linear mathematical deterioration models of USPV of various types of AC mixtures through their fatigue process models were obtained with reasonable coefficients of determination.
- 7- Implication of AAE technology by USPV measurement in the evaluation of AC quality after DITS and microcrack healing process is fast and sound technique for monitoring the

quality control of AC in the laboratory and field, application of such technology is recommended.

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